

Synthesis and Characterisation of *Trans*-Halogenopyridinecarboxamidebis(dimethylglyoximato)cobalt(III) Complexes

V. R. VIJAYARAGHAVAN^a and A. DAYALAN^b

^aDepartment of Physical Chemistry, University of Madras, Guindy Campus, Madras-600 025

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Loyola College, Madras-600 034

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Schrauzer and Kohnle¹ showed that bis(dimethylglyoximato)cobalt(III) complexes (cobaloximes) resemble vitamin-B₁₂. Since then extensive preparative studies were carried out^{2,3} to understand the *trans*-labilising effect in the cobaloximes. Bis(dimethylglyoximato)cobalt(III) complexes undergo electron-transfer reactions with metal ion reductants. Earlier kinetic studies showed⁴ that there is considerable effect of axial ligands on the rate of reduction of cobaloximes. We report herein the synthesis and physical characterisation of some halogenocobaloximes containing pyridinecarboxamide: nicotinamide (nic-CONH₂) or isonicotinamide (isonic-CONH₂), as the other *trans*-ligand.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses (Table 1) are in agreement with the proposed composition. The molar conductivity of all the complexes in methanol lies around 10 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm², indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis%: Found/(Calcd.)			
	C	H	N	Co
[Co(dmgh) ₂ (nic-CONH ₂)Cl]	37.51 (37.63)	4.45 (4.48)	18.75 (18.82)	13.10 (13.20)
[Co(dmgh) ₂ (nic-CONH ₂)Br]	34.12 (34.22)	4.02 (4.07)	17.02 (17.11)	11.80 (12.00)
[Co(dmgh) ₂ (nic-CONH ₂)I]	31.20 (31.23)	3.70 (3.72)	15.50 (15.62)	10.80 (10.95)
[Co(dmgh) ₂ (isonic-CONH ₂)Cl]	37.55 (37.63)	4.40 (4.48)	18.71 (18.82)	12.95 (13.20)
[Co(dmgh) ₂ (isonic-CONH ₂)Br]	34.10 (34.22)	4.00 (4.07)	17.05 (17.11)	11.90 (12.00)
[Co(dmgh) ₂ (isonic-CONH ₂)I]	31.28 (31.23)	3.70 (3.72)	15.49 (15.62)	10.90 (10.95)

Electronic spectra of all the complexes show highly intense bands at 210–220 (4.4–4.5), and 245–270 nm (log ε_{max} = 4.3–4.5 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), which are due to intra-ligand transitions centred in the oxime. The transitions characteristic of the pyridine ring are masked by these intense bands.

The shoulder at 300 nm has been attributed to transitions involving the metal-oxime grouping⁵. The peaks in this region are also sensitive to variations in the axial ligand⁶. These peaks lose their intensity during the reduction of the cobaloxime.

Thus, it is reasonable to attribute these bands to ligand-metal charge-transfer (LMCT) transitions, possibly involving the oxime. The visible spectra of the complexes showed shoulder ca. 425 nm, which was found to be much intense in the case of the iodo complexes. This low energy band may be assigned to the spin-allowed ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} transition⁷ with the other spin-allowed ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} band masked by the intense charge-transfer bands occurring at 300–360 nm.

The ir spectra of the complexes show a medium intense band around 1570 cm⁻¹, which is attributed to the C=N stretching mode; whereas, an intense absorption at 1230 cm⁻¹ is assigned to N—O stretching of the equatorial ligand. The doublet at ca. 3200 and 3400 cm⁻¹ is due to the NH₂ vibration of the amide group of pyridinecarboxamide. The absorption at 1690 cm⁻¹ can be ascribed to the free carbonyl vibration of the amide. Hence, the ir data suggest that the amide group of the pyridinecarboxamides is free and only the pyridine nitrogen is involved in coordination with the metal ion⁸.

The ¹H nmr spectra of all the complexes show singlet at δ 2.30 due to the methyl protons of the dimethylglyoxime. The aromatic protons of nicotinamide appear as multiplet at 7.6–8.5, due to their unsymmetric nature; whereas, the aromatic protons of isonicotinamide appear as well-resolved doublet at δ 7.8 and 8.1. The spectra are similar to those reported in the literature⁹.

Experimental

Samples of cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate, dimethylglyoxime (both S. Merck), nicotinamide and isonicotinamide (both E. Merck) were used as such. Cobalt(II) bromide was prepared by the addition of a calculated amount of 40% aqueous HBr to cobalt(II) carbonate and evaporating the resulting solution to dryness.

trans-[Co(dmgh)₂(nic-CONH₂)Cl] and *trans*-[Co(dmgh)₂(isonic-CONH₂)Cl]: These complexes were prepared by a modified method⁵ from the dichloro¹⁰ complex, H[Co(dmgh)₂Cl₂], where dmgh⁻ = dimethylglyoximato mono anion. A slurry of hydrogen dichlorobis(dimethylglyoximato)cobaltate(III) (3.6 g, 0.01 mol) was prepared in metha-

mol (50 ml). A methanolic solution of the pyridine-carboxamide (nic-CONH₂ or isonic-CONH₂) (1.22 g, 0.01 mol) was added, followed by the addition of 1 drop of glacial acetic acid. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 20–30 min with constant stirring. Completion of the reaction was indicated by the absence of green crystals of the dichloro complex. The brown coloured product was filtered and washed successively with water, methanol and diethyl ether. The complexes were recrystallised from hot methanol, (70–80%).

trans-[Co(dmgh)₂(nic-CONH₂)Br] and *trans*-[Co(dmgh)₂(isonic-CONH₂)Br]: These brown coloured bromo complexes were prepared (60–70%) from the dibromo complex, H[Co(dmgh)₂Br₂], by the same procedure as outlined above for the preparation of chloro complexes.

trans-[Co(dmgh)₂(nic-CONH₂)I] and *trans*-[Co(dmgh)₂(isonic-CONH₂)I]: The dichloro complex, H[Co(dmgh)₂Cl₂] was converted into aquoiodo complex, [Co(dmgh)₂(H₂O)I], as reported in the literature^{3,4}. A methanolic solution of the aquoiodo complex (4.34 g, 0.01 mol in 75 ml CH₃OH) was heated on a water-bath with a methanolic solution of pyridine carboxamide (nic-CONH₂ or isonic-CONH₂, 0.01 mol). The completion of the reaction was indicated by the formation of the dark brown coloured product of iodopyridinecarboxamidebis-(dimethylglyoximate)cobalt(III)-(50–60%).

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were analysed at Indian Institute of Technology, Madras. The cobalt was estimated by the reported method¹¹.

The molar conductivity of the complexes in methanol was measured using a Wayne-Kerr B642 autobalance universal bridge. Electronic spectra (20% CH₃OH–H₂O, v/v) were obtained on a Carl-Zeiss SPECORD spectrophotometer, infrared spectra (KBr) on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra DMSO-d₆ on a Bruker-Pulse CXP-90 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard.

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